

Investigation of the Economic Effects of Natural Disasters in the World and Also Earthquakes on Countries

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Abstract

Turkey was devastated by a series of powerful earthquakes in February 2023, which resulted in substantial property damage and fatalities. The lessons learned from the last earthquake suggest that the effect on Turkey's GDP would likely be transitory. This is because the government of the nation would have committed significant sums of money in rebuilding, which would have resulted in a significant economic resurgence. On the 6th of February, 2023, a series of earthquakes, the greatest of which measured 7.8 on the Richter scale, impacted northern and western Syria in addition to the southern and central regions of Turkey. There have been almost 50,000 fatalities, and many more people are missing after the disaster. In addition to the tragic loss of life that they inflict, natural catastrophes such as this one may do enormous harm to the economy of the affected areas. They not only damage machinery, buildings, and other infrastructure, but they also impede productivity in the process. However, there is a great deal of debate on the precise extent to which these events impacted the output of the economy. According to the findings of study conducted by

2

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Barro and Martin (2003) and Raddatz (2009), there are a considerable number of people who hold the belief that earthquakes and natural catastrophes in general have a major negative impact on the development of economic systems. Recent studies have revealed that there are also significant indirect consequences, such as the economic harm that is disseminated across trade networks and supply chains. Economists call to this phenomena as "spillover effects" (Teh et al., 2011; Ruta et al., 2021). On the other hand, other study has shown that there may be a minor increase in height (Albala-Bertrand, 1993; Loayza et al., 2012; Porcelli and Trezzi, 2019; Skidmore and Toya, 2002). These studies were conducted by Loayza et al., Porcelli and Trezzi, and Skidmore and Toya. According to Hallegatte et al (2022), the economic impact of natural disasters such as these recent earthquakes depends on the amount of destruction they produce, the economic conditions that existed before the event, and a country's capacity to reallocate its resources towards the restoration process. In other words, the economic impact of natural disasters like these recent earthquakes depends on three factors. Poorer economies, such as lower levels of government expenditure and weaker institutions, are likely to have more negative consequences on growth (Cavallo et al., 2013; DuRose, 2023; Lackner, 2018; Noy, 2009; Toya and Skidmore, 2007). This is due to the fact that poorer nations tend to have lower levels of economic activity overall. This is due to the fact that countries with lower levels of wealth are more likely to be adversely affected by factors that have a bigger negative impact on growth. What kinds of insights can we glean from the methods in which other countries have responded to the devastation caused by earthquakes? The researchers were able to establish the country's GDP in the year after the earthquake by using data from prior earthquakes that caused at least 1,000 fatalities, such as those that occurred in Chile, Colombia, Haiti, India, Indonesia, Italy, and Japan. Those earthquakes occurred in those countries. These nations have all shown signs of following this pattern. This reduction will not endure for an extended period of time since major reconstruction will ultimately raise GDP, notably via increases in government expenditure. Cavallo et al. (2013) discovered that the findings of this research are consistent with the findings of previous studies that investigated the repercussions of natural catastrophes on a broader scale.

Keywords: *Natural Disasters, Economic Effects of Earthquakes on Countries, Earthquakes and Their Economic Effects, Economics of Earthquake Impact in Natural Disasters*

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Introduction

The authors' own calculations, as well as data from the Maddison Tables and the Penn World Tables, were used to compile the data used in their estimations of the effect earthquakes have on GDP and government expenditure.

Increases in either the GDP or public expenditure. This growth forecast is based on the assumption that there will be no earthquakes. The left panels are based on an example of 43 earthquakes for GDP and 23 earthquakes for government expenditure, and the confidence intervals suggest that there is a 90% chance that these numbers are accurate.

The Gross Domestic Product is a measure of the economic effect of a catastrophe; nevertheless, its usefulness is relatively restricted. On the other hand, if we look at the overall difference between firms' rates of return and their cost of capital investment (also known as "value added"), we can see that the cost of rebuilding is included in this calculation. This is because "value added" refers to the difference between a company's rate of return and the amount of capital it invests. On the other hand, this does not take into consideration the expenditures that are linked with the damage done to physical assets or to the health of humans. These prices have the potential to skyrocket. According to estimates provided by JP Morgan (2023) and the World Bank (2023), the direct damage caused by earthquakes in Turkey in 2023 is expected to range from \$25 billion to \$35 billion. This includes damage to residential properties, businesses, and infrastructure.

What effect did the 1999 earthquake have on Turkey's gross domestic product?

It is possible to build a counterfactual for the economy of Turkey in the wake of the earthquake that occurred in 1999 by making use of the same study methodology. This refers to the state of the economy in the hypothetical scenario in which there are no earthquakes. It is essential, however, not to lose sight of the fact that the Turkish economy was already in a precarious position in the beginning of 1999, far before the earthquake. This was a direct consequence of a lengthy time during which there was economic unpredictability. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) published a report in July 1999, one month before the earthquake (IMF, 1999), stating that growth for the third quarter of that year was negative and hardly anticipated. This occurred again in the

CURRENT SCIENCE

year 2000, which led to a large rise in the total amount of money that the government spent on the various efforts at reconstruction.

According to the data, the growth performance of Turkey over a period of two years is 4.6 percentage points lower than what was expected based on the non-earthquake scenario (counterfactual). Despite the help that was offered by investments in disaster response, this was nonetheless the result. This forecast does not take into consideration how poorly the business performed during the first six months of 1999. If we exclude this information, we are presented with a somewhat different picture, which indicates that the anticipated economic effect is somewhere in the range of 0.9% of GDP. The estimations obtained from the prior study show that the magnitude of this undesirable impact is rather more than expected. According to these calculations, the gross domestic product decreased by 0.5% to 1% in the year that the earthquake took place, but it increased by 1.5% in the year that followed (Bibbee et al., 2000).

The earthquake that occurred in 1999 had a magnitude that was somewhat lower (7.6) than the earthquake that occurred in 2023; nonetheless, it took place in the industrial hub of Turkey. In 1999, just around 4% of the total population of the nation resided in the four areas that were most badly impacted by the earthquake (Kocaeli, Sakarya, Bolu, and Yalova). On the other hand, these areas were directly responsible for around 7% of the country's GDP and 14% of the value contributed to industrial production. They kept up significant business connections with the rest of the nation, notably in Istanbul and Bursa, which are respectively the biggest and fourth largest cities in Turkey. According to Bibbee et al. (2000), as a direct consequence of the event, severe damage was caused to the infrastructure of the region's energy, transportation, and communication networks.

Methodology

Together, the seriously damaged regions accounted for 35 percent of the country's gross domestic product and 50 percent of the country's industrial production. The earthquake caused interruptions in supply networks, damage to industries, equipment, and food held in storage facilities (loss of physical capital and inventory), fatalities and injuries among workers (loss of labor), and a decline in investment shortly following the earthquake. The early decline in the economy may be attributed

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to the confluence of these several variables. In addition, the failure of many locally held businesses to get earthquake insurance before it was too late led to their demise. On the path leading up to the financial crisis of 2001, this had a domino effect on the banking industry, which saw a huge rise in the number of loans that went into default (Bibbee et al., 2000). This was a direct cause of the catastrophe. On the other side, attempts to restructure contributed to an improvement in development in the year 2000. The earthquakes that struck Turkey in 2023 were quite different from the earthquakes that struck the nation in 1999 in a number of respects. The provinces of Kahramanmaraş, Gaziantep, Malatya, Diyarbakır, Kilis, Sanlıurfa, Adıyaman, Hatay, Osmaniye, and Adana were among those in the southeast area of Turkey that were hit the worst by the recent earthquakes. This region also includes the city of Kahramanmaraş. The pipelines, roads, airports, and energy facilities in these regions were severely damaged, and a massive fire broke out at the Iskenderun port, which is the largest shipping port in Turkey. However, in comparison to how they were in 1999, the economic ties that formerly existed between the impacted districts and the rest of the nation are now in a considerably more precarious state. Despite the fact that they are home to around 15% of the entire population of the nation, the impacted regions only contribute approximately 9%.

It is anticipated that there would be less interruptions to agricultural output as a result of the earthquake taking place during the winter months (Kelly and Kóczán, 2023). This is the case despite the fact that the area contributes more to the value contributed by agriculture than any other (15%). The earthquakes that took place in 2023 took place a significant amount of time before the earthquakes that took place in 1999. Because of this, the beneficial effect that the reorganization will have on the economy will become substantially more apparent within the same calendar year.

In addition, it is expected that the consequences on the financial industry would be less severe since more people have been purchasing earthquake insurance ever since it became widely available in 1999. What are some of the ways in which the earthquakes that are expected to occur in 2023 may impact the economy? The action taken with regard to the budget will largely decide the effect that this will have on the economy. The quantity of public debt (as well as the cost of managing it) is still relatively modest as compared to GDP, which affords politicians the chance to support a diverse array of assistance programs. The World Bank has estimated that the earthquakes caused a total of \$34.2 billion in direct damage, including the costs of rehabilitation

6

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and emergency response, and that the cost of reconstruction would be twice that amount (World Bank, 2023). The Turkish government has pledged more than \$5 billion for rescue and recovery operations as of the time this story was written. The international community's provision of financial aid will also be beneficial to the restructuring measures that are being undertaken. In comparison to the earthquakes that occurred in 1999 and 2023, it is anticipated that the overall effect of the most recent tragedy on economic expansion will be much less than one percent of output in 2023.

However, since search and rescue activities are still ongoing, there is a large amount of uncertainty around these estimations. During the month of February 2023, a series of deadly earthquakes devastated northern and western Syria, as well as the southern and central regions of Turkey. An earthquake with a magnitude of 7.8 was directly responsible for causing extensive property damage as well as the deaths of tens of thousands of people.

In this post, we will offer some early estimations concerning the probable consequences that the earthquake that will occur in February 2023 might have on the economy of Turkey. The earthquake is predicted to take place in Turkey. In the first stage of our investigation, we take a high-level look at the consequences that significant earthquakes have on society as a whole. To do this, we use a technique called synthetic control and build on past research that was conducted on 25 different economies. Following that, we will investigate the ways in which the earthquake that struck Turkey in 1999 had an impact on the surrounding area, and then we will concentrate on the similarities and differences between that earthquake and the one that will occur in 2023. Previous studies have revealed that earthquakes may have a major effect on their surroundings. affects economies. Natural catastrophes such as earthquakes, floods, typhoons, and hurricanes may inflict substantial harm to economies by generating interruptions in production and living, in addition to causing damage to equipment, buildings, and infrastructure. These types of disasters can occur everywhere on Earth. However, there is a lot of controversy around the actual amount to which these impacts have an impact on productivity. It has been argued by a number of academics, notably Barro and I. Martin (2003) and Raddatz (2009), that earthquakes in general, as well as other natural catastrophes, have a considerable negative impact on economic growth. Recent studies (The et al. 2011, Ruta et al. 2021) have shed light on the possibilities of economic spillover that might extend across the whole economy through trade connections and supply networks. On

7

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the other hand, some researchers have demonstrated that it may actually have a good impact on development (Albala-Bertrand 1993, Barone and Mocetti 2014, Caselli and Malhotra 2004, Loayza et al 2012, Porcelli and Trezzi 2019, Skidmore and Toya 2002). These studies can be found in Barone and Mocetti 2014, Barone and Mocetti 2019, Loayza et al 2012, and Porcelli and Trezzi 2019. According to Hallegatte et al., the economic ramifications of earthquakes rely on the degree of damage caused by earthquakes, the economic circumstances before the earthquake, and the ability of the economy to reallocate resources for rehabilitation. All of these factors are interconnected. Poorer economies, as well as those with lower levels of government investment and weaker institutions, are more likely to be impacted by the bigger negative impacts that earthquakes have on growth (Cavallo et al. 2013, DuRose 2023, Lackner 2018, Noy 2009, Toya and Skidmore 2007). This is due to the fact that earthquakes are more likely to occur in regions that are more prone to earthquakes. This is due to the fact that earthquakes often take place in regions that are more susceptible to the repercussions of natural catastrophes. Even within countries, the repercussions are not uniformly dispersed, and the most vulnerable communities are generally the ones who face the brunt of the consequences of natural catastrophes (Colmer 2021). Evidence derived from the synthetic control technique We analyze the average effect of more than 40 large earthquakes that happened in 25 different nations by using the "synthetic control" method. This study makes use of the experiences that countries all over the globe have had following earthquakes that have claimed the lives of at least one thousand people, such as those that have occurred in Chile, Colombia, Haiti, India, Indonesia, Italy, and Japan. The synthetic control method examines the difference between the performance of economies that have been affected by earthquakes and the performance of economies that are analogous to earthquakes but have not been affected by them. These economies were selected as comparators because they have high GDP per capita, fast development in the variable of interest (such as GDP or government expenditure), large populations and high population densities, and all of these characteristics are similar to the economy that is being studied.

In the year after an earthquake, the average GDP in countries that were impacted by the earthquake is around one percentage point lower than in otherwise similar economies; however, the difference is not statistically significant due to the enormous amount of variance in the growth outcomes of the sample.

CURRENT SCIENCE

This impact, like the last one, is only transitory since considerable reconstruction operations are anticipated to boost GDP (especially via increases in government expenditure). These estimations are consistent with those obtained from earlier studies that used a methodology that was very similar to the one utilized by Cavallo et al. (2013) in order to investigate the effects of natural catastrophes on a more extensive scale.

The phrase "synthetic control" refers to a counterfactual growth route that is based on the development of the variable of interest in the weighted average of economies similar to the economy impacted by the earthquake prior to the earthquake in terms of GDP. This growth path is used to determine how the economy would have grown in the absence of the earthquake. Economists were the ones who first came up with the phrase "synthetic control." The earthquake data used for the left panels came from a sample of 41 events for GDP and 23 earthquakes for government expenditure. These earthquakes were selected at random. The 90% level of confidence is indicated for the confidence intervals. It is essential to keep in mind that the Gross Domestic Product is a measure of the economic effect of a catastrophe that has certain inherent limitations. The cost of rebuilding is included into the value generated for a particular year; however, the harm done to people's health or their material possessions is not taken into consideration. These prices have the potential to skyrocket. It is now anticipated that the overall cost of reconstructing housing, productive capacity, and infrastructure following the earthquake would be between \$25 billion and \$50 billion, which is equal to five percent of the country's gross domestic product (for example, JP Morgan, 2023).

Evidence from the earthquake that occurred in Turkey in 1999 Using the same technique, we are able to build a counterfactual for the economy of Turkey after the earthquake that occurred in 1999. Due to the fact that the earthquake that happened in 1999 took place at a time of severe economic instability, the practical application of this study is made more difficult by the bad economic performance that Turkey already suffered in the first half of 1999.

According to the results of our investigation, Turkey's performance in terms of its semi-annual growth was around 4.6 points below what ought to have been projected as a counterfactual. This forecast does not take into consideration how poorly the company performed during the first half of 1999. After taking into consideration this effect, which is the difference between the 4.2%

CURRENT SCIENCE

counterfactual growth rate of synthetic control and the prediction that was released for Turkey in July 1999, it is possible to estimate that the economic impact will be somewhere in the neighborhood of. This negative effect is somewhat larger than the estimates discovered in other research, which imply a loss of between 0.5% and 1% of GDP in the year that the earthquake occurred, followed by a gain of 1.5% in the year that followed (Bibbee et al. 2000). This unfavorable impact is about one and a half times more severe than the estimations obtained from prior investigations. Location of the Earthquake in 1999 The earthquake that happened in Turkey in 1999 was significantly less powerful than the earthquake that took place in 2023; yet, it took place smack dab in the midst of the country's industrial center. Kocaeli, Sakarya, Bolu, and Yalova were the areas of the nation that were most hit by the earthquake in 1999, yet they were home to just around 4% of the country's total population. On the other hand, these areas were directly responsible for around 7% of the country's GDP and 14% of the value contributed to industrial production. It maintains substantial business relationships with other parts of the nation, particularly with Istanbul and Bursa, which are, respectively, Turkey's biggest and fourth largest cities. According to Bibbee et al. (2000), as a direct consequence of the event, severe damage was done to the infrastructure of the energy, transportation, and communication systems of the broader area. Together, the seriously damaged regions accounted for 35 percent of the country's gross domestic product and 50 percent of the country's industrial production. The earthquake caused interruptions in supply networks, loss of physical capital, labor, and inventory, as well as decreased investments in the immediate aftermath of the tragedy. These aspects of the situation helped to bring about the first slump in the economy. There were a great number of locally owned companies that, had they purchased earthquake insurance, could have been able to avoid closure. This had a domino effect on the banking industry, which saw a considerable rise in the number of loans that were deemed to be non-performing in the run-up to the financial crisis that took place in 2001 (Bibbee et al., 2000). This contributed to the crisis that took place in 2001. On the other hand, actions connected to restructuring contributed to the rise in growth that occurred in the year 2000. The earthquake that hit Turkey in 2023 was quite different from the earthquake that happened in 1999. A comparison of the economic repercussions of the catastrophes that occurred in 1999 and 2023 is shown below.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The larger area in southeastern Turkey that was struck by earthquakes in February 2023 (Kahramanmaraş, Gaziantep, Malatya, Diyarbakır, Kilis, Sanliurfa, Adıyaman, Hatay, Osmaniye, Adana) with pipelines, highways, airports, and the port of Iskenderun, which is the biggest port in Turkey. The significance of the electrical infrastructure, which included the big fire, cannot be overstated. On the other hand, the economic connections that formerly existed between the impacted regions and the rest of the nation are much more tenuous today than they were in 1999. Despite the fact that they are home to around 15% of the overall population of the nation, the impacted regions only contribute approximately 9% of the GDP of the country and 10% of the industrial value added. Although the timing of the earthquake during the winter months is expected to have a mitigating impact on the interruptions in agricultural output, the contribution of agriculture to value added is larger, at 15% (Kelly and Kóczán 2023), and this is despite the fact that the earthquake occurred during the winter months. The earthquake in 2023 took place significantly earlier in the year than the one in 1999 did. As a consequence of this, the effects of the rebuilding will manifest themselves mostly during the same calendar year, which will greatly mitigate the detrimental effects of the earthquake. The GDP fell as a direct result of these factors. Because earthquake insurance is more widespread now than it was in 1999, the effects that it has on the financial services industry are also anticipated to be less severe. Possible effects that will be brought on by the earthquakes in 2023 The financial reaction to the earthquake will play a very significant part in deciding the effects that the earthquake will have on the economy. As a result of the fact that both the total amount of public debt and the cost of payment are still relatively low in comparison to GDP, the government is in a position to support a wide range of various assistance programs without being constrained financially. When this article was published, the government had already pledged more than one hundred billion pounds, which is equal to five billion dollars, to the relief and recovery operations, and donations from the outside community might help fund the reconstruction efforts even further. When the synthetic control study and the comparative analysis of earthquakes in 1999 and 2023 are taken into account, the total effect on growth is predicted to be less than one percent of output in 2023. This conclusion was reached after taking into account both studies. a rise in the overall amount of money spent by the government. However, considering that search and rescue efforts are still underway as of the time this article was written, it is important to view these numbers with a healthy dose of skepticism.

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The majority of the time, the economic cost of natural disasters is characterized in terms of the physical consequences they have, such as the damage of assets, the loss of harvests, the costs of rebuilding, and other similar expenses. However, the experience of a catastrophe also has a psychological and emotional influence on people; it alters the manner in which individuals think, the way in which they behave, and the way in which they make decisions, including economic judgements. When seen in this light, the psychological repercussions of a catastrophe may continue to have substantial effects on the economy for a long amount of time after rebuilding has been completed. Available

The results go counter to what is generally accepted as true in the economics field. People who live in places that are prone to natural disasters have a responsibility to take safety measures to protect themselves and their families from the devastation and suffering that natural disasters may cause. It is not surprising that the mentality of "saving for a rainy day" has been so firmly ingrained in all of our minds. This phenomenon, which economists refer to as "consumption smoothing" and which has been the subject of much research (Rosenzweig and Stark, 1989; Udry, 1995), illustrates the way in which people put money aside in anticipation of difficult times and then utilize those savings to get through those difficult times. Because of this, the majority of economic theories hypothesize that individuals who go through a natural or man-made disaster would start to take preventative measures against future catastrophes, such as increasing the amount of money they store. In contrast, the findings of the team's investigation indicated the complete opposite to be the case. The region of Sichuan in China, which was struck by a powerful earthquake in 2008, served as the major focus of this study.

Literature Study

The majority of the villagers, the researchers found, expressed a desire to "enjoy life as long as it goes" rather than be concerned with making preparations for an earthquake. The group discussed whether or not this mindset might expand to other economic behaviors such as spending and saving, as well as whether or not they could evaluate the implications of these activities using data from the economy. It just so happened that in 2007 some of the places that were hit the most were surveyed, and as a consequence, data from before the earthquake were received. The researchers

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were able to establish comparisons between "before" and "after" states because they carried out follow-up questionnaires in 2009 and 2011. In other words, families and households who did not suffer any monetary losses as a consequence of the earthquake but were nevertheless emotionally scarred by the incident despite the fact that they did not lose any material possessions. When we take into account changes in external variables like price or job prospects, any changes in the observed behavior of such families would then be driven by "psychological" factors. This is because "psychological" factors take into account individuals' thoughts, feelings, and experiences. This is due to the fact that "psychological" elements take into consideration the ideas, emotions, and experiences of a person. The attention of the researchers was concentrated on the following three endeavors:

This was not the result of any shifts in their earnings, which were unaffected by the earthquake's effect on their location because of the quake. There was no correlation between the distance from the epicenter and shifts in family income; however, there was a correlation between the distance and shifts in household expenditures. The Epicurean philosophy seems to be reflected in all three of these actions. In terms of their economics (they save less), and their health (they drink more), households who are geographically closer to the epicenter seem to have evolved a stronger propensity to accept risks.

The conduct of people who experienced the earthquake is consistent with the notion that such individuals are more prone to "live as if there is no tomorrow," to use a saying. Because of the multifaceted nature of the circumstance, it is difficult to accurately assess the effects that might result from such a shift of perspective. The additional costs could provide a little bit of a boost to the economy of the surrounding region, but drinking and gambling won't be one of them. In addition, it is unknown what takes place over a longer span of time at this point. The authors are able to demonstrate that the impacts persisted for a period of three years after the earthquake and into 2011, which is a considerable amount of time after the reconstruction was finished; however, there is no evidence beyond this point. Those who, in the aftermath of the earthquake, developed the behaviors of spending money, drinking alcohol, and playing mahjong are likely to continue engaging in these activities in the long run. On the other hand, it is conceivable that they may eventually develop a new fear of earthquakes, which would prompt them to return to economic life. Not only did the earthquake have an impact on the ways in which people invest and spend

CURRENT SCIENCE

their money, but it also stunted the growth of enterprises in the region as a whole.

A significant amount of aid for recovery and reconstruction was provided to the areas that were impacted by the earthquake. Because of the flood of help, prices for local products and services, as well as the salaries of local employees, have skyrocketed. The manufacturing sector has grown less competitive as a direct consequence of this, as a result of having to match product pricing and wage levels with those in the national market. Following the earthquake, there was a discernible reduction in the percentage of the region's overall industrial output that was contributed by seismic zones. However, it is probable that factories and other types of infrastructure in the areas that were impacted by the earthquake were damaged, which would have a direct effect on the amount of industrial output. The author of this essay starts out by doing an analysis of the bordering counties of seismic districts that were not affected by the earthquake in order to have a better understanding of the influence that enhanced municipal services and wages have had on industry productivity.

There is a possibility that the disruption created by the earthquake in the districts that were damaged by the earthquake may influence the production network of the districts that are close, and as a result, the quantity of industrial output in these bordering districts will decrease. In order to rule out the possibility of this happening, the paper conducts further research on investment flows between earthquake-prone counties and the counties that border them, and it discovers that between the years 2001 and 2015, there was no obvious trend.

The increasing prices of non-tradable commodities, which were driven by enormous transfer flows, most of which were bilateral assistance, lured workers away from the local manufacturing sector and into the local service sector. This resulted in a net loss of jobs in the manufacturing sector. The manufacturing industry was unable to readily modify the cost of its products. As a direct consequence of this, there has been a momentary drop in the level of profitability experienced by the manufacturing sector in the most recent period.

Findings

Consequently, a mix of techniques for dealing with and rebuilding after natural disasters, such as widely dispersed interventions, outsourcing, and good coordination among players at different levels and across sectors, may boost resilience to natural disasters and, as a result, decrease the

CURRENT SCIENCE

magnitude of economic damage. This is something that is mentioned in a book that was published in 2016 by Chen et al. that draws lessons from the earthquake that occurred in the Sichuan region of China in 2008. The events of the earthquake in 2008 serve as the inspiration for this work. The tendency of those who are likely to be impacted by the catastrophe to save money may assist not just China but also other nations in increasing their resistance to the impacts of natural disasters.

Former member of the IFPRI Research Fellowship Program Mateusz at the present time, Filipski is serving in the capacity of assistant professor in the department of agricultural and applied sciences at the University of Georgia. Professor of Economics and DSGD Senior Research Fellow at the National Development School at Peking University, Xiaobo Zhang is a recognized authority in the field of development economics. Urbanization, population increase, environmental degradation, changes in land use, insufficient governance, climate change, and poverty and inequality in susceptible locations are common types of vulnerabilities. Natural calamities are the culprits in each of these cases. Other natural phenomena, in addition to geophysical dangers, include hydrological hazards (such as floods, landslides, and wave movements), meteorological hazards (such as storms and significant temperature fluctuations), and climatological hazards (such as drought, forest fires, and glacial lakes). explosions). Each of these natural disasters has the potential to endanger human lives and cause damage to property.

The majority of them have a single characteristic, and that is the harm that they inflict, whether it is the loss of life, the devastation of property, or something altogether else. On the other hand, some natural catastrophes have the potential to inflict far more damage and, thus, higher expenses over time. This is true for geophysical dangers, in particular earthquakes. Each year, the Earthquake Information Center documents more than 20,000 earthquakes, with an average of 55 earthquakes occurring each and every day. As an example, there were around 2,200 earthquakes of magnitude 5.0 or greater that took place in 2021. Earthquakes are one of the natural disasters that take place the most regularly and profoundly impact human civilization as a result. This effect may be seen in the areas of economics, society, and the environment.

Social Repercussions Caused by Earthquakes

15

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It is possible that the social repercussions of earthquakes are the most significant of all the results that have been listed. This is due to the fact that severe seismic occurrences often inflict a significant number of injuries in addition to fatalities. The number of persons who were impacted by earthquakes between the years 1998 and 2017 was estimated to be 125 million by the Disaster Epidemiology Research Center (CRED). In contrast, the number of deaths caused by earthquakes was 747,234, which is a much larger number. fatalities brought on by more forms of natural catastrophes. When we speak about the societal effect of seismic occurrences, however, we are not simply talking about the fact that people lose their lives. It is also true that many houses and infrastructures may be badly damaged or destroyed by earthquakes. People lose their houses and their things, and many of them end up having to live on the streets as a consequence of earthquakes. More than 65 million people have been forced to relocate as a direct result of earthquakes that have occurred since the year 1900. This number is climbing higher as a direct consequence of an increase in general population as well as a higher population density in every region of the planet. The interruption of essential resources, such as clean water supplies, is yet another issue that earthquakes bring to the attention of society.

When analyzing the long-term consequences that earthquakes have on a society, the state of the population's health is an essential factor to take into consideration. Not only does the number of people who die as a direct result of earthquakes rise, but "[...] a decrease in health and care insurance is observed in the month of the earthquake." [Citation needed]" In spite of this, "[...] the proportion of fatal outcomes dropped after earthquakes." One hypothesis that may be able to explain this improvement is the use of cutting-edge engineering procedures in nations all over the globe.

[Economic Impact of Earthquakes](#)

The social and economic repercussions that earthquakes have on a society are inextricably intertwined; these repercussions may have either a short-term or a long-term influence on the civilization. In the short term, earthquakes often result in the destruction of businesses, industries, and essential components of the physical environment. However, in the long run, the impacts of earthquakes are contingent not only on the condition of the country's infrastructure but also on the

CURRENT SCIENCE

economic standing of the nation. Additionally, the destruction of roads and railways, among other things connected to transportation, has a negative influence on the economy since it complicates commercial ties. This is another factor that contributes to unfavorable economic outcomes. The economy is often subject to both short-term and long-term repercussions after an earthquake. Rebuilding a nation's housing stock, infrastructure, or transportation networks is often included in the category of long-term economic consequences. This is because of the need of doing so.

According to studies conducted by the World Research Center for Disaster Epidemiology (CRED), the direct financial impact of earthquakes on the global economy was at least \$661 billion between the years 1998 and 2017.

Impact of Earthquakes on Environment and Society

There is one additional consequence that earthquakes have, despite the fact that their social and economic repercussions are sometimes considerably more severe than those of other natural catastrophes. It is essential that this aspect be taken into consideration, and that aspect is the impact that earthquakes have on their surroundings. Despite the fact that earthquakes' effects on the environment are not usually as noticeable as their effects on society and do not necessarily have the same financial weight as earthquakes' effects on the economy, these effects may nonetheless be fairly important. When it comes to the environment, earthquakes that range from mild to severe have the ability to wreak havoc, ruining both natural and man-made landscapes, raising the possibility of gas lines breaking, and eventually starting fires and contaminating the whole region. In addition, earthquakes represent a danger to the wildlife that lives in forests because they often trigger further natural catastrophes such as landslides and tsunamis, all of which have the capacity to eradicate all plant and animal life in a region. Intense seismic activity often has repercussions that are felt very immediately, but there is also the potential for longer-term harm to occur. "One of the most widespread or long-term environmental repercussions of an earthquake is the destruction of historically important places, whether those sites were naturally occurring or were created by humans.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Relationship Between Individual Earthquake Effects

Although each of the aforementioned earthquake impacts has the potential to produce major damages both immediately and over a longer period of time, these effects are also strongly intertwined with one another and influence one another. This is true not just for the social and economic repercussions, but also for the interactions that occur between those two impacts and the environmental implications. When social ramifications, such as the loss of life and injuries to people, occur in an impacted region, the local economy of that area suffers severe damage as a result. In this specific example, we are discussing the costs of treatment as well as the expenditures associated with insurance; nonetheless, the reduction in the working population has a negative impact on the economy. This is due to the fact that often a huge workforce is required in order to repair the infrastructure and services that were damaged in an earthquake. Another socioeconomic effect of earthquakes is a decrease in GDP per capita, which eventually leads to a general deterioration in quality of life. This is a direct consequence of earthquakes. There is a connection between earthquakes and this impact. Another element that leads to a decline in quality of life is an earthquake's potential to pollute the surrounding environment via its aftereffects. This factor contributes to a heightened risk of illness among the general population, which has a substantial impact on the health of individuals. Another factor that has an effect not only on the environment but also on the economy owing to the threats it presents to agriculture is the destruction of the landscape. This is a factor that has an influence not only on the environment but also on the economy. In addition, the effects that earthquakes have on the surrounding ecosystem might have a negative impact on the economy.

There is often a considerable impact felt in other businesses, particularly the tourist industry. Using socio-economic indicator techniques similar to those described in Daniell et al. (2010a), we will do further reanalysis in order to better understand indirect losses in the Asia-Pacific region. To what degree are seismic occurrences responsible for producing capital losses and upheaval in various areas of the economy, which in turn causes production to vary from its trend? The discussion on this topic has been reignited as a result of recent big occurrences such as the "Tohoku" earthquake that occurred in Japan in 2011 and the "Aquilano" tragedy that occurred in Italy in 2009; nevertheless, no agreement has been achieved in the literature on this problem as of yet. In spite of the fact that earlier contributions (which will be discussed further below) relied on

CURRENT SCIENCE

completely different identification methodologies, three primary empirical challenges have emerged.¹ To begin, seismic events are massive, one-of-a-kind shocks that occur on a local scale; yet, their overall significance is often quite low. collective terms, in particular in economies that are more developed. The use of national data ultimately results in the generation of estimations of mitigation. Second, earthquakes are very uncommon, and most of the time, there are no counterfactuals. Third, while the moment magnitude (as measured on the Richter scale) is often used as a purely exogenous regressor, there is only a modest correlation between it and the severity and extent of earthquakes. In contrast to the research that has been done before, which has concentrated almost solely on the outcomes at the aggregate level (the national level), we find that there is also a local component. By using the data provided by the provinces, it is feasible to assess the effects of earthquakes with a higher degree of precision, particularly those earthquakes that only inflict damage in a subset of the provinces. Because of the association between the Richter scale and the earthquake, we also utilize the Mercalli scale rating, which is a geophysical method established to classify seismic damages in twelve notches, ranging from "instrumental" to "catastrophic" (XI2).

The Mercalli scale is an indicator that is used to measure the loss of capital stock at the local level. This scale is based on a narrative description of the severity of the losses. Scale is the foundation of this explanation. During the empirical study that we are going to do, we are going to conduct fixed-effects regressions, and one of the things that we are going to do is examine the rate of change of provincial output as an alternative dependent variable. We are able to identify the impacts of seismic activity in two different ways: as a regressor, or more specifically, as an exogenous dummy variable (Mercalli). For every province that has at least one municipality with a Mercalli rating above III) or the provincial Mercalli rankings (the highest or highest average of the ranks that were given to municipalities).

Both of these choices are open to consideration. It is possible to make use of the square of the Mercalli order as a regressor, which makes it possible to capture nonlinearities in the behavior of output (as well as employment). Carry out instrumental variables regressions that make use of the geophysical features of each event (moment-magnitude and distance from the epicenter of each province) as entirely exogenous instruments. Because of this, any possible internality problems about the Mercalli rankings will be eliminated. Our results, which were confirmed using a wide

CURRENT SCIENCE

variety of different tests, indicate to three important implications. To begin, we provide evidence that does not support the hypothesis that earthquakes have a significant bearing on the level of economic activity. This finding is accurate both in the year when the occurrence took place and in the medium term (horizon of five years). In spite of the fact that the point estimates derived from our regressions have a negative sign, the standard errors are relatively wide in each model, which indicates that the coefficients are not statistically distinct from zero. When the employment rate is used as the dependent variable, one arrives at the same conclusion as before.

Second, if we restrict our investigation to the central provinces that, on average, report the greatest and most extensive damage, we still arrive at the same conclusions. To put it another way, our data is compelling "at any level of harm," which includes the most catastrophic occurrences. This is due to the fact that the negative spillover effects from the province that is the epicenter to the other provinces have been measured at a level that is considered to be minimal.

Understanding How Earthquakes Affect Their Victims Charles Francis Richter, an American physicist, collaborates with Beno Gutenberg in the year 1935. At the California Institute of Technology, he devised a method to quantify the quantity of energy that is generated during an earthquake. Both the Richter and the Mercalli ratings measure the intensity of an earthquake. Richter and Gutenberg established a base-10 logarithmic scale, which is often referred to as the 'Richter moment magnitude scale' (or simply the 'Richter scale'). The 'seismic moment' of the earthquake is what is utilized to calculate the magnitude of the quake. In order to calculate the size of the slip region, the stiffness of the Earth is multiplied by the typical amount of slip that occurs on the fault, and the size of the slip zone is used as the basis for the calculation. A magnitude 6.0 earthquake has a 'swing amplitude' that is 10 times bigger than a magnitude 5.0 earthquake, and this is also related with a 31.6 times greater energy release. The Richter scale is used to measure the intensity of earthquakes. In today's modern world, seismographs are the devices of choice for documenting the intensity of earthquakes. On the other hand, before seismographs were invented, another scale was devised to categorize the severity of earthquakes. The year 1783 saw Pompeo Schiantarelli and Ignazio Stile, two Italian architects, came up with a simple scale to quantify the damages inflicted by the catastrophic event that occurred in the southern portion of the peninsula in that year. This meter is intended to be used in the process of determining the degree to which

20

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something has been damaged. The scale, which has been subject to a number of modifications throughout the course of its history, is currently known as the "Mercalli scale," named after the Italian volcanologist Giuseppe Mercalli, who made the modification to the scale in 1908.

Conclusion

Since the 1970s, there has been a huge rise in the amount of money spent to repair the damage caused by natural catastrophes. According to research done by Guha-Sapir et al. (2015), the record-breaking earthquake that took place in Japan in 2011 caused damages of around 380 billion US dollars. These losses are equivalent to the GDP of the whole planet. Comparable to 0.9%. Natural catastrophes have been shown to have a major negative influence on the short-term macroeconomic performance of many nations, according to several studies that have been published in peer-reviewed academic journals. This is due to the fact that these natural catastrophes have a major negative influence not only on the economic growth rates of countries but also on their external performance, price levels, financial systems, and fiscal sustainability (see, for example, Felbermayr and Grosch, 2014; Skidmore and Toya 2002; Noy 2009; Loayza et al.). Significant obstacles that might hinder the operation of a nation's economy. When faced with the challenges that arise in the aftermath of a natural catastrophe, the fundamental goal of monetary authorities is to quickly restore economic stability. Natural catastrophes, on the other hand, provide the standard challenge. This means there is just one difficulty. causes a deficit in the amount of product that is created, which results in a brief, negative divergence from the path of balanced development (Felbermayr and Groschl 2014; Loayza et al. 2012; Klomp 2016; Fomby et al. 2013). In order to jumpstart the economy's recovery and get things back on track as soon as possible, the central bank can decide to stimulate aggregate demand and conduct an expansionary monetary policy. But there is a risk of higher inflation if the attitude of monetary policy is loosened during a time when domestic output is temporarily low. This scenario has the potential to play out. Natural disasters, on the other hand, raise the marginal costs of local producers, which puts upward pressure on the general price level (Cavallo et al. 2014; Heinen et al. 2019; Parker 2018). If central banks want to prevent any future increase in the inflation rate, they will need to adopt a more

CURRENT SCIENCE

contractionary approach to monetary policy. On the other side, the output will reduce even more in the event that this approach is adhered to. This paradox illustrates that, in the wake of a cataclysmic event, the nation's central banks are not capable of both stimulating the economy and bringing inflation under control in reaction to the crisis. Finding a middle ground between these two opposing concerns is the most effective course of action that should be taken in the early aftermath of a catastrophe. This contractionary approach is mostly driven by the Federal Reserve's anti-inflationary tendency, which says that the nominal interest rate should react primarily to increased inflation rather than to lower production. This shows that the Federal Reserve's anti-inflationary trend is the primary driver behind this strategy. Because of this inherent bias, the Central Bank decided to implement a policy that is contractionary. On the other hand, the results of a number of other examinations point in the complete other direction. For instance, White (1997) contends that growth should be prioritized above low inflation when it comes to monetary policy, since the first impacts of inflation after the majority of natural catastrophes are only transitory, local, and concentrated in a select few industries. This is due to the fact that inflationary pressures have a tendency to be concentrated in certain regions.

As a consequence of this, the topic of whether or not monetary policy ought to be loosened or tightened in the aftermath of a natural catastrophe is one that is widely contested, and the answer, at least in a theoretical sense, is that it depends on various components of monetary policy being in place. The question of whether decisions on monetary policy are made by an independent central bank or, alternatively, by a central bank that is more politically bound is one of the most fundamental areas of dispute in this discussion. As a consequence of the changes that have taken place in many nations over the course of the last two decades, the monetary authorities of a great number of nations now enjoy a greater degree of autonomy, freer from the direct sway of political authority. It is a widely held assumption that if central banks were given the option, they would cave in to the pressure put on them by politicians. These politicians may be motivated by short-term political considerations, or they may exaggerate short-term economic expansions while underestimating the long-term inflationary impacts of expansionary policies (Walsh 2005). Either way, these politicians may be overestimating the benefits of expansionary measures on the economy. For whatever reason, many people believe that central banks are susceptible to the pressure that politicians exert on them. If the ability of politicians to alter monetary policy leads

CURRENT SCIENCE

to hyperinflation, then nations that have a central bank that is independent of political influence should see lower rates of inflation. Indeed, there is a plethora of empirical data to support this argument, which implies that independent central banks (CBIs) may play a major role in attaining low inflation (Cukierman 2008, Crowe and Meade 2007, and Klomp and De Haan 2010a). This assertion argues that independent central banks (CBIs) can play an essential role in obtaining low inflation.

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